

Economic Influence through Exhibit Marketing in Relation to Military : Case Study of DSA 2018 and 2022

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Abstract

Exhibit Marketing is a ploy to display products and entities for the purpose of giving exposure to the public with regards to the attributes of the products. The exhibitions or trade fairs had in numerous ways contribute to the alleviation of influences of the companies, organizations, and also the countries. As more consumers acquire the products, the economy of that particular country would appreciate, especially the manufacturing sector of that particular country. This paper delineated the statistical count of the Exhibit Marketing of Defence Services Asia for the years 2018 and 2022 and the influences of these trade fairs in tandem with economic benefits.

Introduction

Defence Services Asia (DSA) is the premier exhibition of services and products pertaining to military entities such as hardware, software, apparels, and others. Examples of prominent products are helicopters, tanks, unmanned aerial vehicle, airplanes, assault weapons, and others. DSA featured well established companies and organizations such as Airbus, British Aerospace, and several notable marine, air, and land companies. DSA was not held in 2020 due to the Covid-19 pandemic. As mentioned, this paper dissected the statistical values of DSA 2018 and 2022 in order to gauge the intensity of DSA in tandem with the efforts by companies of certain countries to promote their products.

According to Soilen, Exhibit Marketing is a trade fair which adhered to the context of principles of marketing [1]. Soilen pointed out that Exhibit Marketing is fairly complex with intricacies in developing booths that have the aesthetic beauty to attract consumers [1]. In his book, he iterated the importance of collecting data in order to understand the attitude of consumers in relation to the displayed products and he mentioned the methods to attract more consumers [1].

In order for the products to be sold in volumes that are appropriate to garner profits, the personnels in charge of the marketing should be productive and proactive in approaching potential clients during the trade fair or exhibitions. Harridon had investigated factors of productivity and it's imperative for organizations or companies to identify leverages to be given to personnel in order to increase their productivities [2].

The marketing ploy or activities subsequently would contribute to the appreciation of influences of the organizations and inadvertently the countries that hosted these organizations would be affluent in terms of economic vibrancies as products are acquired and manufactured and hence increasing the GDP of the country. Blesa and Ripolles indicated that marketing that was done effectively would increase the economic stature of a country [3]. They also mentioned the sphere of economic vitality

where an efficient marketing, be it via exhibitions or meetings or conferences, would attract investments from various parties to invest in the designated countries [3].

Literature Review

There are several modes of marketing where the primary interest is to convey information and attract potential customers. Siskind iterated that Exhibit Marketing is a method to create the right and appropriate image in order to acquire substantial revenues, through sales, from consumers [4]. Siskind denoted that in Exhibit Marketing the personnel involved are required to facilitate or go through face-to-face interaction with the customers where this approach would gain emotional trust from the customers [4].

DSA mainly provides products within the military realm. Military products are acquired by nations to upgrade their defences and also to increase their force multipliers. The acquisition of military products is complex and requires protocols to be met. According to Zsifkovits and et. al., the acquisition of the products should be cost effective and also inline with policies set by the government [5]. The purchase is not a straight forward process but involves myriad agencies in the government where the gist is to eradicate any financial leakages [5].

With the acquirements, the firm or company would be tasked to manufacture the products within a stipulated time frame. If the number of acquirements is voluminous and high, extensive manufacturing process would be actuated and this in turn would contribute to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of the nation. Harridon had elucidated the GDP values of nations in tandem with the Manufacturing Sector of the designated nations and the Manufacturing Sector was denoted as a vital component to the appreciation of GDP of nations [6].

Marketing had played a significant role in alleviating the economy of organizations and subsequently the nation. There were numerous instances of these circumstances and Kuada had denoted notable examples in his paper [7]. He however had pointed out that the economic benefits were not properly bestowed or trickled upon the masses and only the urban populations were benefactors of such economic rewards [7].

Pitta and et. al. had delineated the benefits of actuating Exhibit Marketing where there are proper or sufficient approaches to gain a more holistic outcome through exhibitions [8]. They were critical of the developments of Exhibit Marketing and they also stated that any alterations of the approaches in Exhibit Marketing would have an effect upon the rewards that would be acquired [8].

It is also imperative for products to be exhibited or sold be at its optimum state or stature. Harridon mentioned incidents of a particular type of helicopter that was imparted by incidents which had taken a toll upon the good name of the company [9]. It is sufficient to indicate that any maladies involving a product should be eradicated or lessen in order to market the product effectively and this eventually would increase the chances of actuating sales. And an increase in sales would aid the manufacturing sector of the nation and thus producing an economy that is more vibrant and energetic.

In this paper we had classified the data of the exhibition into several categories. This ensures the analyses of the data are comprehensive, easy, and in a structured manner. Classification methods have been utilized by myriads of researchers in order to gain meaningful analyses of various subjects. Kiang had investigated the advantages of using classification methods and she stated that classification methods were usually applied by companies to drive business decisions [10]. She also iterated that classifications allow companies to strategize better and make more in depth tractions pursuant to marketing [10].

Evidently classification method is a useful approach and hence we had applied such method in our paper. Our method is further supported by other researchers, such as Hand, that indicated that classification methods were used in various industries such as medicine, business, psychology, and others [11]. Hand had measured and evaluated these classification methods and had stipulated that these classification methods can be graded via numerical metrics [11].

Marketing had played an enormous role in appreciating the economy of a nation. As more goods are sold and purchased, the GDP of the country would increase, in a linear or exponential manner for a determined period of time. Bakator and et. al. had studied this phenomenon and they found out that there is a relationship between marketing and economy of a country [12]. Their study had concentrated upon the economy of Serbia where brands were also investigated to show correlation with the emerging economy of Serbia [12].

Tafesse and Skallerud had mentioned that Exhibit Marketing could be classified into 2 types which are vertical type and horizontal type [13]. In vertical type, the products that are exhibited are concentrated upon pedantic theme while horizontal type exhibits products that are in a sense broad and thus various themes of products are on displayed [13]. This gave us the impression that Exhibit Marketing is taken seriously where various research had been published with regards to its functionalities and advantages. Our research upon Exhibit Marketing is validated as this area was numerously denoted as vital to the economic ecosystem.

Methodology

The analyses were actuated based upon the methodology shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The Methodology Pertaining to Analyses of Exhibit Marketing of DSA 2018 and 2022

For the analyses of Exhibit Marketing, Defence Services Asia 2018 (DSA 2018) and Defence Services Asia 2022 were chosen as subjects to be investigated and analysed. Data from these two events were extracted where the exhibitors of DSA 2018 and 2022 were classified in accordance to their countries of origin. The number of exhibitors were tabulated in accordance to their country and within the contextual period of 2018 and 2022.

The incremental or decremental values of the exhibitors, pursuant to their obligations in 2018 and 2022 respectively, were calculated and tabulated. The rate of these increments or decrements were also calculated based upon the 4 years period where the rate was consigned to a value per year. The exhibitors were also classified in accordance to their regions in order to observe the intensities of the regions in promoting their military entities and products.

The number of exhibitors from each region was also tabulated and this gave us clear indications of the gravity of their efforts in spreading their economic influences upon numerous countries. With the results of the analyses, we proceeded in discussing the impacts of the exhibitors in tandem with the economics influences that were abounded.

Results

This section portrays the results of the analyses and investigations that were actuated upon the data of DSA 2018 and 2022.

Figure 2. Number of Exhibitors of DSA 2018 in Accordance to Their Countries

Figure 3. Number of Exhibitors of DSA 2018 in Accordance to Their Countries

Figure 4. Number of Exhibitors of DSA 2018 in Accordance to Their Countries

Figure 5. Number of Exhibitors of DSA 2018 in Accordance to Their Countries

Figure 6. Number of Exhibitors of DSA 2018 in Accordance to Their Countries

Figure 7. Number of Exhibitors of DSA 2018 in Accordance to Their Countries

Figure 8. Number of Exhibitors of DSA 2022 in Accordance to Their Countries

Figure 9. Number of Exhibitors of DSA 2022 in Accordance to Their Countries

Figure 10. Number of Exhibitors of DSA 2022 in Accordance to Their Countries

Figure 11. Number of Exhibitors of DSA 2022 in Accordance to Their Countries

Figure 12. Number of Exhibitors of DSA 2022 in Accordance to Their Countries

Figure 13. Increment or Decrement of Exhibitor

Figure 14. Increment or Decrement of Exhibitor

Figure 15. Increment or Decrement of Exhibitor

Figure 16. Increment or Decrement of Exhibitor

Figure 17. Increment or Decrement of Exhibitor

Figure 18. Increment or Decrement of Exhibitor

Figure 19. Increment or Decrement of Exhibitor

Figure 20. Increment or Decrement of Exhibitor

Figure 21. Increment or Decrement of Exhibitor

Figure 22. Increment or Decrement of Exhibitor

Figure 23. Increment or Decrement of Exhibitor

Figure 24. Increment or Decrement of Exhibitor

Figure 25. Increment or Decrement of Exhibitor

Figure 26. Increment or Decrement of Exhibitor

Figure 27. Rate of Increment or Decrement

Figure 28. Rate of Increment or Decrement

Figure 29. Rate of Increment or Decrement

Figure 30. Rate of Increment or Decrement

Figure 31. Rate of Increment or Decrement

Figure 32. Rate of Increment or Decrement

Figure 33. Rate of Increment or Decrement

Figure 34. Rate of Increment or Decrement

Figure 35. Rate of Increment or Decrement

Figure 36. Rate of Increment or Decrement

Figure 37. Rate of Increment or Decrement

Figure 38. Rate of Increment or Decrement

Figure 39. Rate of Increment or Decrement

Figure 40. Rate of Increment or Decrement

Table 1. Regions of the Exhibitors and Total Exhibitors – DSA 2018

Region	Country	Total Number of Exhibitors
South Asia	India, Pakistan, Bangladesh	25
East Asia	Taiwan, Philippines, Malaysia, Hong Kong, Singapore, China, Thailand, Republic of Korea, Japan, Indonesia, Vietnam	294
Middle East	Turkey, UAE, Kazakhstan, Bahrain, Lebanon	94
Europe	Czech Republic, UK, Greece, Austria, Italy, Sweden, France, Germany, Finland, Netherlands, Poland, Switzerland, Bulgaria, Spain, Belarus, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Denmark, Belgium, Croatia, Romania, Slovakia, Ukraine, Russia, Portugal, Hungary, Serbia, Slovenia, Norway, Estonia, Latvia, Montenegro	340
Africa	South Africa, Egypt, Ivory Coast	38
North America	USA, Canada,	128
Central America	Ecuador, Costa Rica	2
South America	Brazil, Colombia, Peru, Argentina	9
Oceania	Australia, New Zealand	63

Table 2. Regions of the Exhibitors and Total Exhibitors – DSA 2022

Region	Country	Total Number of Exhibitors
South Asia	India, Pakistan	17
East Asia	Malaysia, Republic of Korea, Thailand, China, Singapore, Japan, Indonesia, Hong Kong, Taiwan	261
Middle East	UAE, Turkiye, Lebanon, Azerbaijan, Saudi Arabia, Oman,	61
Europe	UK, Russia, Sweden, France, Poland, Switzerland, Italy, Austria, Belgium, Spain, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Germany, Netherlands, Czech Republic, Slovakia, Portugal, Romania, Norway, Hungary, Finland, Denmark, Lithuania, Greece, Ukraine, Latvia, Belarus	236
Africa	South Africa	2
North America	USA, Canada	41

Central America	None	0
South America	Brazil	1
Oceania	Australia, New Zealand	6

Discussion

Analyses had shown that Malaysia was the biggest exhibitor at DSA 2018 with 125 exhibitors from Malaysia had exhibited their products. At DSA 2018, USA is the second biggest exhibitor with 114 exhibitors from USA taking part in the exhibition. It is well known that USA is one of the biggest suppliers of weaponries in the world and their participation in DSA 2018 is perhaps to increase their foothold and influences upon the military industry. A huge chunk of the economy of the USA is within the contextual layout of exporting military products ranging from fighter airplanes to missiles. The military industry in the USA is valued at USD 541.6 billion in 2021 and it is expected to grow tremendously in the coming years [14]. With this in mind, the companies originated from USA has an important role to sell their products in order to sustain their military industry and hence retain their economic position within this realm.

Malaysia as the host of DSA 2018 had the homegrown advantage to exhibit their products with minimal cost as the transportation cost of transporting cargoes and personnel to the exhibition venue is low in contrast to international exhibitors that have to bear the high cost of transporting their goods. The number of exhibitors from Malaysia in 2018 implied that the military industry in Malaysia is thriving and with the announcement of the government in 2023 with regards to the purchase of new fighter aircrafts, there would be spillages to companies in the genre of aircraft maintenance, spare parts acquirement, training, and others and this in totality would enhance the industry to a level which is rewarding to the masses.

In DSA 2018, the region that contributed the most exhibitors was Europe with a combined total of 340 exhibitors. This shows organizations in Europe have the latest technologies to showcase and bestow upon those that are interested to increase their force multipliers. Europe is also the cradle of technologies where countries such as Finland, Norway, UK, France, and others are constantly emphasizing upon innovations and this subsequently led to improvements of current products. Countries seeking for upgrades would benefit from these improvements where the Original Equipment Manufacturers (OEM) would introduce an Upgrading Programme to their existing customers. Exhibitions such as DSA is the appropriate platform to parlay such programme.

The classification of exhibitors into regions was deemed necessary as we could extract vital analyses from this classification. Harridon had utilized classification in his research and this led to extraction of different perspectives of the intended subjects and this shows classification is a good approach to gain meaningful nuances [15]. Mayilvaganan and Kalpanadevi agreed with this notion and they had utilized classification techniques to categorize data in order to predict the performances of students [16].

The region with the least exhibitor in DSA 2018 was Central America where it was represented by only 2 exhibitors. This is perhaps because the region does not have the significant number of companies that are heavily involved in the military industry and hence the products produced are few and could possibly not cater for a vast military market.

In 2022, DSA was carried out where a total of 50 countries took part. This was pale in comparison with DSA 2018 where 63 countries took part. Perhaps the Covid-19 pandemic had taken its tool where countries were still recovering from the pandemic and these countries preferred to concentrate upon

other industries for their economic liberalization. In DSA 2022, Malaysia as the host country had 156 exhibitors. The reason for this high value is similar to the reason given for DSA 2018. But for the year 2022 the number of exhibitors had increased in contrast to the year 2018 where there were only 125 exhibitors. The reason for this increase was perhaps the catalyst provided by the government to aid industries in Malaysia in order to alleviate the economy of the country after a disastrous showing during Covid-19 pandemic. According to Business Today, the government of Malaysia had injected RM530 billion into the economy of Malaysia for the period 2021 till 2022 and this stimulus package had seen the GDP of Malaysia remained competitive after the post Covid-19 period [17]. The stimulus package involved the necessary aids to Small Medium Enterprises (SMEs) to uphold their statures and some these SMEs were involved in the military industry.

As mentioned before, the marketing actuations through diverse means such as conferences and exhibitions had bestowed benefits upon the economies of the nations. This gist had attracted the USA where USA had sent a strong delegation of 39 exhibitors for DSA 2022. Even though this was a steep depreciation of the number of exhibitors, the team from USA was still formidable with legacy companies like Colt's Manufacturing, Honeywell International, Lockheed Martin, and others exhibiting their products at DSA 2022. These companies are big and contributed significantly to the GDP of the USA throughout the years.

The rate of depreciation of the USA from 2018 till 2022 was 18.75 exhibitors per year. This value of depreciation is high and comparable to another country, South Africa, which had depreciated at 8.5 exhibitors per year. The highest appreciation was 7.75 exhibitors per year which was recorded by Malaysia. This was indeed a significant approach to market products by Malaysian companies for the sake of increasing the GDP of Malaysia. It has to be noted that some of these products were produced in collaboration with other companies originating from other countries.

In DSA 2022, the biggest number of exhibitors was from the East Asia region with a total number of 261 exhibitors. We can observe the likes of Japan and Korea taking proactive approaches to widen their sphere of influences which can be attributed to their desire to widen their economic outreach. The marketing of their products through Exhibit Marketing was indeed substantial in tandem with the agreement inked by Japan and Malaysia in the year 2018 where the agreement spelled out the military activities and technology transfer between both countries.

Conclusions

The actuation of Exhibit Marketing had given advantages to the exhibitors and their respective countries with regards to the increase of economic influences imparted by those designated countries. Numerous countries at various regions have significant footholds in the Military Industry and it's imperative for them to market their products perpetually in order for them to be sustainable and profitable. There were valid justifications to engage upon Exhibit Marketing and one primary justification was the need to sustain the economy of a nation through sellable products. The United States of America has a solid platform within the contextual military realm where this particular area had contributed greatly to their GDP. Analyses upon DSA 2018 and 2022 had indicated an active role by the United States of America to expand and retain their niche in the Military Sector. But other countries were proactive as well as indicated by our analyses.

References

- [1] Soilen, K.S., "Exhibit Marketing and Trade Show Intelligence", Springer, ISBN 978-3-642-36792-2, Berlin Heidelberg 2013
- [2] Harridon, M., "Factors that Affect Productivity of Aircraft Maintenance Personnel at KLIA2", Journal of Tianjin University Science and Technology, Volume 54, Issue 12, December 2021, ISSN 0493-2137, DOI : 10.17605/OSF.IO/ZB85E
- [3] Blesa, A., and Ripolles, M., "The Influence of Marketing Capabilities on Economic International Performance", International Marketing Review, Volume 25, Number 6, Pages 651-673, DOI : 10.1108/02651330810915574
- [4] Siskind, B., "Powerful Exhibit Marketing : The Complete Guide to Successful Trade Shows, Conferences and Consumer Shows", ISBN-10 0-470-83469-2, John Wiley & Sons Canada Ltd, 2005
- [5] Zsifkovits, M., and et. al., "A Systematic Analysis of Military Equipment Acquisition Among NATO Suppliers : A Proof of Concept Based on a Multi-Layered DSS Approach", Proceedings of the Fourteenth Annual Acquisition Research Symposium, Volume 2, April 26-27, 2017, Naval Postgraduate School, Monterey
- [6] Harridon, M., "Trends of Gross Domestic Product from Manufacturing of Four ASEAN Countries : A Period of 25 Years", Sky Orbital Centre for Human Advancement (SOCHA), Volume 1, Issue 1, Pages 1-10, February 2023, DOI : 10.5281/zenodo.7633521
- [7] Kuada, J., "Marketing, Economic Growth, and Competitive Strategies of Firms in Africa", African Journal of Economic and Management Studies, Volume 7, Issue 1, Pages 2-8, DOI : 10.1108/AJEMS-02-2016-0014
- [8] Pitta, D.A., and et. al., "Integrating Exhibit Marketing into Integrated Marketing Communications", Journal of Consumer Marketing, Volume 23, Number 3, Pages 156-166, April 2006, DOI : 10.1108/07363760610663312
- [9] Harridon, M., "Analyses of Incidents of Helicopter Guimbal Cabri G2 : Analyses of Pilots", International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications, Volume 11, Issue 5, May 2021, ISSN 2250-3153, DOI : 10.29322/IJSRP.11.05.2021.p11311
- [10] Kiang, M.Y., "A Comparative Assessment of Classification Methods", Decision Support Systems, 35, 2003, 441-454, DOI : 10.1016/S0167-9236(02)00110-0
- [11] Hand, D.J., "Assessing the Performance of Classification Methods", International Statistical Review, 2012, 00, 00, 1-15, DOI : 10.1111/j.1751-5823.2012.00183.x
- [12] Bakator, M., and et. al., "Transition Economy and Market Factors : The Influence of Advertising on Customer Satisfaction in Serbia", Economic Research, Volume 32, Issue 1, 2019, Pages 2293-2309, DOI : 10.1080/1331677X.2019.1642787
- [13] Tafesse, W., and Skallerud, K., "A Systematic Review of the Trade Show Marketing Literature : 1980 – 2014", Industrial Marketing Management, 2016, DOI : 10.1016/j.indmarman.2016.11.001
- [14] Mordor Intelligence, "United States Defense Market – Growth, Trends, Covid-19 Impact, and Forecasts (2023-2028)", US Defense Market Analysis, Hyderabad, 2022
- [15] Harridon, M., "Analysis of Uniform of Flight Attendants of Air Asia via Classification and Discrete Observation", International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications, Volume 12, Issue 3, March 2022, ISSN 2250-3153, DOI : 10.29322/IJSRP.12.03.2022.p12308
- [16] Mayilvaganan, M., and Kalpanadevi, D., "Comparison of Classification Techniques for Predicting the Performance of Students Academic Environment", 2014 International Conference on Communication and Network Technologies, 18-19 December 2014, Sivakasi, India, DOI : 10.1109/CNT.2014.7062736

[17] Business Today, “Govt Successfully Overcomes Post Covid-19 Pandemic Economic Challenges”, Editor’s Choice, September 2022, Reach Publishing Sdn Bhd